

Hierarchical Normalized Completely Random Measures for Complex Network Data

Francesco Gaffi

Department of Applied and Computational Mathematics and Statistics,
University of Notre Dame, Indiana, USA

Abstract

There is an increasing availability of complex network data encoding connectivity information among a set of nodes belonging to different layers. When such layer division is induced by categorical characteristics of the nodes, we talk about *node-colored* networks. In such framework, inferring grouping structures among nodes based on common connectivity patterns, while considering the layer division, as well as predicting connectivity behaviour of unobserved nodes, are particularly challenging tasks. By letting such connectivity blocks to coincide with the layers, one fails to learn sub-blocks within each layer as well as across-layer clusters. To flexibly incorporate layer information instead, a new generation of partially exchangeable stochastic block models relying on random partition priors induced by hierarchical normalized completely random measures has been proposed in [11]. The partial exchangeability assumption among nodes according to layer division allows to infer both within- and across-layer blocks, while preserving probabilistic coherence and allowing for uncertainty quantification. The connate projectivity of these nonparametric priors, entails theoretically-guaranteed edge prediction for unobserved batches of nodes simultaneously joining the network. In this paper we summarize the results contained in [11].

Keywords: Bayesian nonparametric, partial exchangeability, multilayer network

1. Introduction

Network theory is widely employed to describe and analyze complex systems in social, biological, physical and engineering sciences. Consequently, methodological investigations regarding the analysis of network data are more and more spread in the statistical literature. As the systems that need to be modeled become more structured, as the urge for models able to encode different information at several levels increases. Multilayer networks are a prominent example of such elaborated systems: on top of the usual network structure, given by nodes linked by edges, they include layerizations of the network itself, according to characteristics of the nodes, of the edges or both, accounting for, *e.g.*, *intra-* and *inter-*layer connections, several dimensions of layerization, copies of the same node existing in different layers, and so on. For insightful

reviews on multilayer networks, see [5] and [20]. When the layerization is given by a univariate characteristic of the nodes, we talk about *node-colored networks*, while if it is given by a feature of the edges, they are named *edge-colored networks*. Modeling such networks naturally represents a challenging statistical task: in order to take into account the entirety of such structures but still being able to perform reliable inference on features of the network as well as validated predictions on unobserved parts of it, we want to stick to a model-based and fully probabilistic approach.

One of the most significant tasks in the analysis of networks is the detection of grouping structures based on the connection activity of the nodes. See *e.g.* [13, 1, 21]. Early approaches have often relied on community detection algorithms, as in [16, 26, 25, 4]. These methods are focused on recognizing groups with dense connectivity inside and sparse communication outside, and hence tend to oversimplify the grouping structure. On the other hand, also spectral clustering techniques, which show better flexibility properties, have been employed. See *e.g.* [33]. However, such algorithms lack of an integrated statistical procedure allowing for joint modeling of different aspects of the clustering, like the number of groups, as well as uncertainty quantification for inference and prediction. More on the side of a model-based approach lie stochastic block models (SBMs). See [17] and [27]. In this class of models, the partition of the nodes is a latent feature of the network: for each couple of nodes, the probability of creating an edge is given conditionally on the allocations of the couple. In a Bayesian framework, in order to perform inference on such allocations, a prior is placed on the space of partitions and a posterior distribution is retrieved by updating the prior according to the observed connections. This entails the inference of block structures made of nodes sharing the same patterns of communication with the members of all the blocks, hence allowing for the recognition of more complex and connectivity-driven grouping structures. The favorable ratio between simplicity of the structure and flexibility of the inferred clustering, together with the availability of easy and efficient inference techniques, have brought to further developments and generalizations of such models, encompassing also the use of more and more flexible priors on the random partition, from the classical Dirichlet-multinomial, to the Dirichlet process and mixture-of-finite-mixtures, as in [31], [19] and [15]. For a general framework under the unifying concept of Gibbs-type priors, a careful comparison and an insightful application to criminal networks, see [22].

As mentioned, the incorporation of more complex network structures requires the formulation of new models, or extensions of existing ones, to take such complexities into account. With a general focus on edge-colored networks, this has been done *e.g.* in [23, 32, 28, 10, 12, 3, 35, 8, 29, 18, 14, 2]. Following this line, but crucially moving the focus on the widespread node-colored networks, that encompass a single notion of connectivity among nodes which uniquely belongs to different layers, and fulfilling the need of theoretically-guaranteed prediction schemes, we introduced in [11] a new generation of partially exchangeable stochastic block models (pEx-SBMs). Such constructions include the layers' division information leveraging a partially exchangeable latent array of nodes' attributes, obtained as realization from hierarchical normalized completely random measures (H-NRMIs). These nonparametric priors, defined in [6], represent the natural generalization of the normalized completely random measures (NRMIs), introduced in [30], to the partially exchangeable scheme as intended in [9]. The natural parallel between partially exchangeable random arrays and node-colored networks is described in details in [11]. Thanks to the sequential nature of the prior that H-NRMIs induces on the space of consistent sequences of partitions,

pEx-SBMs are built for confronting complex predictive tasks, such as clustering new batches of nodes joining the network simultaneously and estimating their connections with old nodes and among themselves. In [11] predictive performances of pEx-SBMs are showcased, as well as comparisons with state-of-the-art methods in node clustering and community detection.

In this paper we summarize some of the results obtained for the pEx-SBMs in [11]. Such class of models represents a first step towards an integral treatment of general multilayer networks based on representing complex network structures via suitable distributional invariance hypotheses. See the discussion in [11] for an account of this open research direction.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. In Section 2, we present the pEx-SBMs, as in [11]. In Section 3 we cover inference and prediction techniques, based on the collapsed Gibbs sampler devised in [11]. Finally, we give a demonstration of the potentialities of these models reporting the results of the analysis of a synthetic data set, inspired by criminal networks, in Section 4.

2. Model construction

In a node-colored network, we have a set of V nodes which are divided in d layers, according to some characteristic. Each layer $j = 1, \dots, d$ has V_j nodes and $\sum_{j=1}^d V_j = V$. We enumerate the nodes as $\{1, \dots, V\}$, with nodes $\{1, \dots, V_1\}$ belonging to layer 1, nodes $\{V_1 + 1, \dots, V_1 + V_2\}$ belonging to layer 2 and so on. Consequently, an equivalent way of identifying a node is by the couple (j, i) with $j = 1, \dots, d$ and $i = 1, \dots, V_j$. Edges are admitted both across and within layers. Such a structure is usually described by a *supra*-adjacency matrix \mathbf{Y} , which is a block matrix, whose generic entry y_{vu} is 1 if an edge exists between node v and node u and zero otherwise, and whose diagonal blocks are the adjacency matrices of each layer, while the off-diagonal blocks represent the across-layer connections, for each couple of layers. Following the classical Bayesian SBM construction for \mathbf{Y} as in, e.g. [27], we suppose that each y_{vu} is a Bernoulli random variable with success probability determined by the allocations of node v and u in a latent partition represented by the vector $\mathbf{z} = (z_1, \dots, z_V) \in \{1, \dots, H\}^V$, where H is the number of clusters. We consider a $H \times H$ probability block connectivity matrix \mathfrak{E} , whose generic entry $\xi_{hh'}$ is the probability of success of every y_{vu} such that $z_v = h$ and $z_u = h'$. Conditionally on the allocations and such block-probability matrix, Bernoulli trials are independent. As customary, we adopt an independent beta prior for the entries of the block-probability matrix. Hence, conditionally on the latent partition, we can summarize the model as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{Y} \mid \mathbf{z}, \mathfrak{E} &\stackrel{\text{ind}}{\sim} \text{Bernoulli}(\mathfrak{E}) \\ \mathfrak{E} \mid \mathbf{z} &\stackrel{\text{iid}}{\sim} \text{beta}(a, b) \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

for some $a, b > 0$.

We complete the model with a partially exchangeable partition prior (pExP) for the allocations vector \mathbf{z} , as described in [11]. A pExP is defined by a partially exchangeable partition probability function (pEPPF), object introduced in [6] that characterizes the law of the random partition induced by the ties in a partially exchangeable random array directed by a vector of hierarchical normalized completely random measures (H-NRMIs). Such random array, with d rows (one per layer) and V_j columns in the j -th

row (one per node in each layer), for $j = 1, \dots, d$, expresses a latent attribute of the nodes. The partial exchangeability of its distribution induce homophily among nodes in the same layer and allows for heterogeneity across layers, as noted in [11]. In symbols, we define the vector \mathbf{z} as follows. Let $\mathbf{X} = (x_{ji})_{j=1, \dots, d}^{i=1, \dots, V_j}$ be a random array such that

$$x_{j1}, \dots, x_{jV_j} \mid (\tilde{P}_1, \dots, \tilde{P}_d) \stackrel{\text{iid}}{\sim} \tilde{P}_j, \quad \text{for each } j = 1, \dots, d \quad (2)$$

where the vector of random measures

$$(\tilde{P}_1, \dots, \tilde{P}_d) \sim \text{H-NMRI}(\rho, \rho_0, c, c_0, P_0) \quad (3)$$

for positive measurable functions ρ, ρ_0 , positive constants c, c_0 , and a diffuse probability measure P_0 , which determine the H-NRMI distribution as described in [6] and [11]. Now, let the array $\mathbf{Z} = (z_{ji})_{j=1, \dots, d}^{i=1, \dots, V_j}$ be defined as

$$z_{ji} = h \quad \text{if and only if} \quad x_{ji} = x_h^* \quad \text{for } h = 1, \dots, H \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{x}^* = (x_1^*, \dots, x_H^*)$ is the vector of unique values of \mathbf{X} , and let us then consider the vectorized version of \mathbf{Z} , given by $\mathbf{z} = (z_1, \dots, z_V)$. We summarize such definition writing

$$\mathbf{z} \sim \text{pExp}(\mathbf{V}; \rho, \rho_0, c, c_0) \quad (5)$$

for $\mathbf{V} = (V_1, \dots, V_d)$ the vector of numerosities of the layers. The prior in (5) probabilistically incorporates the information of the division in d layers of the nodes according to some latent characteristic, inducing homophily among nodes in the same layer and allowing for heterogeneity across-layers.

3. Inference and prediction

Under (1), the likelihood reads

$$p(\mathbf{Y} \mid \mathbf{\Xi}, \mathbf{z}) = \prod_{h \geq h'=1}^H \xi_{hh'}^{m_{hh'}} (1 - \xi_{hh'})^{\bar{m}_{hh'}} \quad (6)$$

where

$$m_{hh'} = \begin{cases} \sum_{v,u=1}^V y_{vu} \mathbb{1}_{\{z_v=h, z_u=h'\}} & h \neq h' \\ \sum_{v>u=1}^V y_{vu} \mathbb{1}_{\{z_v=z_u=h\}} & h = h' \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

and

$$\bar{m}_{hh'} = \begin{cases} \sum_{v,u=1}^V (1 - y_{vu}) \mathbb{1}_{\{z_v=h, z_u=h'\}} & h \neq h' \\ \sum_{v>u=1}^V (1 - y_{vu}) \mathbb{1}_{\{z_v=z_u=h\}} & h = h' \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Since the objective of our inference is the latent partition \mathbf{z} , *i.e.* the clustering, we marginalize out the connection probabilities $\mathbf{\Xi}$ by leveraging beta-binomial conjugacy, obtaining

$$p(\mathbf{Y} \mid \mathbf{z}) = \prod_{h \geq h'=1}^H \frac{\text{B}(a + m_{hh'}, b + \bar{m}_{hh'})}{\text{B}(a, b)}. \quad (9)$$

where $B(\cdot, \cdot)$ denotes the beta function. We target the posterior distribution $p(\mathbf{z} | \mathbf{Y})$. As described in [11], we can rely on a collapsed Gibbs sampler, based on the full conditionals

$$\mathbb{P}(z_v = h | \mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{z}^{-v}) \propto \mathbb{P}(z_v = h | \mathbf{z}^{-v}) \frac{p(\mathbf{Y} | z_v = h, \mathbf{z}^{-v})}{p(\mathbf{Y}^{-v} | \mathbf{z}^{-v})}, \quad (10)$$

for any node $v \in \{1, \dots, V\}$. Now, the ratio in (10) is easily managed, thanks to (9), and gives

$$\frac{p(\mathbf{Y} | z_v = h, \mathbf{z}^{-v})}{p(\mathbf{Y}^{-v} | \mathbf{z}^{-v})} = \prod_{u=1}^V \prod_{h'=1}^{H^{-v}} \frac{B(a + m_{hh'}^{-v} + r_{vh'}, b + \bar{m}_{hh'}^{-v} + \bar{r}_{vh'})}{B(a + m_{hh'}^{-v}, b + \bar{m}_{hh'}^{-v})}, \quad (11)$$

where $m_{hh'}^{-v}$ and $\bar{m}_{hh'}^{-v}$ are obtained as in (7) and (8), respectively, but disregarding node v in the sums, while

$$r_{vh'} = \sum_{\substack{u=1 \\ u \neq v}}^V y_{vu} \mathbb{1}_{\{z_u = h'\}} \quad (12)$$

and

$$\bar{r}_{vh'} = \sum_{\substack{u=1 \\ u \neq v}}^V (1 - y_{vu}) \mathbb{1}_{\{z_u = h'\}}. \quad (13)$$

For what concerns $\mathbb{P}(z_v = h | \mathbf{z}^{-v})$ we rely on the variable augmentation scheme presented in [11], and typical of a pExp prior: the clustering enforced by H-NRMIs, which we encode in \mathbf{z} , can be obtained as coalescence of a nested sub-clustering, whose allocation vector we call \mathbf{w} , following the notation in [11], and that is the natural result of the hierarchical structure of such nonparametric priors. The subclustering in \mathbf{w} is out of our inferential interests, but it is needed for characterizing the predictive structure of the clustering in \mathbf{z} : as showed in [11], we leverage the joint conditionals $p(z_v, w_v | \mathbf{z}^{-v}, \mathbf{w}^{-v})$ to obtain a posterior sample of \mathbf{z} . Notice that such variable augmentation does not affect the ratio in (10), since, by construction, $\mathbf{Y} | \mathbf{z} \perp\!\!\!\perp \mathbf{w}$. A detailed algorithm is given in [11] to obtain the desired posterior sampling.

Let us now consider k new nodes joining the network simultaneously. We know their layer membership, but we do not observe their connections. The task is to predict the edges that they will create with old nodes and among themselves. We leverage the observed connections and the inferred posterior clustering of the old nodes, together with the projectivity of the model, to perform such prediction. We target $p(\mathbf{Y}^{\text{new}} | \mathbf{Y})$, where \mathbf{Y}^{new} is made of the unobserved edges $y_{v_{\text{new}}u}$, with $v_{\text{new}} = V + 1, \dots, V + k$ and $u = 1, \dots, v_{\text{new}} - 1$. Let $\mathbf{z}_{\text{new}} = (z_{V+1}, \dots, z_{V+k})$ represent the latent allocations of the new nodes and $\bar{\mathbf{z}} = (\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{z}_{\text{new}})$. Then we can write the predictive probability as a linear functional of the posterior partition distribution:

$$p(\mathbf{Y}^{\text{new}} | \mathbf{Y}) = \int p(\mathbf{Y}^{\text{new}} | \mathbf{Y}, \bar{\mathbf{z}}) \mathcal{L}_Y(d\bar{\mathbf{z}}) \quad (14)$$

where \mathcal{L}_Y indicates the posterior law of $\bar{\mathbf{z}}$. The integrand $p(\mathbf{Y}^{\text{new}} | \mathbf{Y}, \bar{\mathbf{z}})$ is expressed in [11] in terms of total number of edges and non-edges between clusters involving old and new nodes. Samples from \mathcal{L}_Y can be obtained completing the output of the Gibbs sampler described above, giving samples from the posterior of \mathbf{z} , with samples from the predictive scheme $p(\mathbf{z}_{\text{new}} | \mathbf{z})$. Notice that such sequential approach is only

Figure 1: The true edge probability matrix (left), simulated *supra*-adjacency matrix (middle) and estimated edge probability matrix under pEx-SBM (right). The columns coloring refers to layers division, the rows coloring displays the true clusters (left and middle matrix) and the estimated ones with pEx-SBM (right matrix). The color of each entry ranges from white to black as the corresponding edge probability goes from 0 to 1.

possible when the prior entails a proper urn scheme: this is not the case for models incorporating the layer division as a covariate in a product partition model fashion. See [24, 22]. Without this sampling scheme, such prediction task could not be confronted in a principled way.

(14) yields the predictive probability of any configuration for the unobserved part of the network, and can be estimated by Monte Carlo approximation as described. However, given the high cardinality of the space of such configurations, a marginal predictive summary for each new edge, such as

$$\mathbb{P}(y_{v_{\text{new}}u} = 1 \mid \mathbf{Y}) = \int \frac{a + m_{\bar{z}_v \bar{z}_u}}{a + b + m_{\bar{z}_v \bar{z}_u} + \bar{m}_{\bar{z}_v \bar{z}_u}} \mathcal{L}_{\mathbf{Y}}(d\bar{\mathbf{z}}) \quad (15)$$

is also derived in [11], where for easing the notation we let $\bar{z}_v := \bar{z}_{v_{\text{new}}}$. Again, the predictive new edge probability in (15) can be estimated via Monte Carlo approximation.

4. Simulations

In order to showcase the performances of pEx-SBM in comparison to available competitors as [36, 22, 4, 7], we report here the results of the analysis of a simulated data set, whose generation is inspired by connectivity patterns typical of criminal networks. We have $V = 80$ nodes divided in $d = 4$ layers, of size $V_1 = V_2 = 30$, $V_3 = 15$ and $V_4 = 5$. In Figure 1, the layers are represented by the columns coloring: red, blue, green and purple. The true connectivity block structure in the first three layers is given by three large within-layer clusters (the dark shade of each layer-specific color, in the rows coloring of Figure 1), three small within-layer clusters (the light shade) and one common across-layers cluster (in white). The purple layer coincides with a cluster instead, for a total of $H_0 = 8$ true clusters. Thinking of a criminal network, in which nodes are criminals and connections represent communications, the rationale behind such structure is the following. Each layer represents a criminal clan, the large within-layer clusters are made of the operatives, the small within-layer clusters comprise the

Table 1: Performance comparison between pEx-SBM and competitors: number of clusters in $\hat{\mathbf{z}}$, and VI distance $\text{VI}(\hat{\mathbf{z}}, \mathbf{z}_0)$ of the estimated $\hat{\mathbf{z}}$ from the truth \mathbf{z}_0 . For both JCDC and SBM (*greed*) a favorable implementation is considered with routines’ initializations at the true number of groups $H_0 = 8$.

	\hat{H}	$\text{VI}(\hat{\mathbf{z}}, \mathbf{z}_0)$
pEx-SBM (H-DP)	8	0.109
Supervised ESBM (DP)	7	0.653
JCDC ($w_n = 5$)	7	1.948
JCDC ($w_n = 1.5$)	4	1.428
SBM (<i>greed</i>)	5	1.358
Louvain	4	1.744

clan-specific supervisors, while the across-layer cluster represents higher-level supervisors, who directly communicate with the purple layer, which coincides with the global bosses cluster. Operatives of the same clan have dense communication among them, fairly dense communication with their clan-specific supervisors, but sparse communication with other clans’ operatives and supervisors, higher-level supervisors and global bosses. The higher-level supervisors serve as liaison between clan-specific supervisors, who have sparse communications across-layers, and are the only ones directly referring to the global bosses, who have very dense communication only among themselves. The connection probabilities expressing such hierarchical structure are illustrated in the left column of Figure 1. Based on such probabilities, we simulate the *supra*-adjacency matrix in the middle column of Figure 1 from independent Bernoulli variables, and then estimate the posterior clustering under pEx-SBM. More specifically, a hierarchical Dirichlet process prior (H-DP) with parameters $(\theta = 0.5, \theta_0 = 4)$ and a beta(1, 1) prior are employed for the partition and the probabilities, respectively. A point estimate of the posterior partition in terms of variation-of-information (VI) distance is obtained through the R library `mcclust.ext` [34].

A comparison with the Louvain algorithm for community detection [4], the *greed* implementation by [7] of the single-layer SBM (that do not consider the layer division information), the JCDC algorithm [36], and the supervised ESBM [22] (that include the layer division information) is illustrated in Table 1, in terms of number of clusters in the point estimate of the partition, and VI distance of the point estimate from the true partition. Recall that, for $V = 80$ the maximum for the VI distance between two generic partitions is $\log_2 80 = 6.32$. See [34]. Moreover, notice that the hyperparameters chosen for the H-DP prior in pEx-SBM enforce a prior expected number of clusters of ≈ 5 . See [11] for more detailed and extended simulation studies.

From these results it emerges that community detection algorithms, being structured to infer dense-within/sparse-across connectivity patterns, fail to recognise more complex hierarchical and core-periphery structures, even when layer informed. The supervised ESBM by [22] allows for the detection of such diverse connectivity structures, via a full-Bayesian inference that combines Gibbs-type priors and product partition models. This guarantees improvements, but the lack of a projective construction undermines the possibility of performing edge prediction for new nodes joining the network. The evaluation of the predictive methods under pEx-SBM on 10 randomly-

selected held-out nodes, yields a mean squared error of 0.027 between the true and the predicted edge probabilities. Such prediction accuracy is remarkable, given that only layer information is employed. The predictive power of pEx-SBM is further showcased in [11], also in applications to real data.

References

- [1] E. ABBE, *Community detection and stochastic block models: recent developments*, J. Mach. Learn. Res., 18 (2017), pp. 6446–6531.
- [2] A. A. AMINI, M. S. PAEZ, AND L. LIN, *Hierarchical stochastic block model for community detection in multiplex networks*, Bayesian Anal., In press (2023).
- [3] P. BARBILLON, S. DONNET, E. LAZEGA, AND A. BAR-HEN, *Stochastic block models for multiplex networks: an application to a multilevel network of researchers*, J. R. Stat. Soc. Series A Stat. Soc., 180 (2017), pp. 295–314.
- [4] V. D. BLONDEL, J.-L. GUILLAUME, R. LAMBIOTTE, AND E. LEFEBVRE, *Fast unfolding of communities in large networks*, J. Stat. Mech.: Theory Exp., 2008 (2008), p. P10008.
- [5] S. BOCCALETTI, G. BIANCONI, R. CRIADO, C. I. DEL GENIO, J. GÓMEZ-GARDENES, M. ROMANCE, I. SENDINA-NADAL, Z. WANG, AND M. ZANIN, *The structure and dynamics of multilayer networks*, Phys. Rep., 544 (2014), pp. 1–122.
- [6] F. CAMERLENGHI, A. LIJOI, P. ORBANZ, AND I. PRÜNSTER, *Distribution theory for hierarchical processes*, Ann. Stat., 47 (2019), pp. 67 – 92.
- [7] E. CÔME, N. JOUVIN, P. LATOUCHE, AND C. BOUVEYRON, *Hierarchical clustering with discrete latent variable models and the integrated classification likelihood*, Adv. Data Anal. Classif., 15 (2021), pp. 957–986.
- [8] C. DE BACCO, E. A. POWER, D. B. LARREMORE, AND C. MOORE, *Community detection, link prediction, and layer interdependence in multilayer networks*, Phys. Rev. E, 95 (2017), p. 042317.
- [9] B. DE FINETTI, *Sur la condition d'équivalence partielle*, Actual. Sci. Ind., (1938), pp. 5–18.
- [10] D. DURANTE, D. B. DUNSON, AND J. T. VOGELSTEIN, *Nonparametric Bayes modeling of populations of networks*, J. Am. Stat. Assoc., 112 (2017), pp. 1516–1530.
- [11] D. DURANTE, F. GAFFI, A. LIJOI, AND I. PRÜNSTER, *Partially exchangeable stochastic block models for multilayer networks*, In revision, (2023).
- [12] D. DURANTE, S. PAGANIN, B. SCARPA, AND D. B. DUNSON, *Bayesian modelling of networks in complex business intelligence problems*, J. R. Stat. Soc. Series C Appl. Stat., (2017), pp. 555–580.
- [13] S. FORTUNATO AND D. HRIC, *Community detection in networks: A user guide*, Phys. Rep., 659 (2016), pp. 1–44.
- [14] L. L. GAO, D. WITTEN, AND J. BIEN, *Testing for association in multiview network data*, Biometrics, 78 (2022), pp. 1018–1030.

- [15] J. GENG, A. BHATTACHARYA, AND D. PATI, *Probabilistic community detection with unknown number of communities*, J. Am. Stat. Assoc., 114 (2019), pp. 893–905.
- [16] M. GIRVAN AND M. E. NEWMAN, *Community structure in social and biological networks*, Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A., 99 (2002), pp. 7821–7826.
- [17] P. W. HOLLAND, K. B. LASKEY, AND S. LEINHARDT, *Stochastic blockmodels: First steps*, Soc. Networks, 5 (1983), pp. 109–137.
- [18] B.-Y. JING, T. LI, Z. LYU, AND D. XIA, *Community detection on mixture multilayer networks via regularized tensor decomposition*, Ann. Stat., 49 (2021), pp. 3181–3205.
- [19] C. KEMP, J. B. TENENBAUM, T. L. GRIFFITHS, T. YAMADA, AND N. UEDA, *Learning systems of concepts with an infinite relational model*, in Proceedings of the 21st National Conference on Artificial Intelligence - Volume 1, 2006, pp. 381–388.
- [20] M. KIVELÄ, A. ARENAS, M. BARTHELEMY, J. P. GLEESON, Y. MORENO, AND M. A. PORTER, *Multilayer networks*, J. Complex Netw., 2 (2014), pp. 203–271.
- [21] C. LEE AND D. J. WILKINSON, *A review of stochastic block models and extensions for graph clustering*, Appl. Netw. Sci., 4 (2019), pp. 1–50.
- [22] S. LEGRAMANTI, T. RIGON, D. DURANTE, AND D. B. DUNSON, *Extended stochastic block models with application to criminal networks*, Ann. Appl. Stat., 16 (2022), pp. 2369–2395.
- [23] P. J. MUCHA, T. RICHARDSON, K. MACON, M. A. PORTER, AND J.-P. ONNELA, *Community structure in time-dependent, multiscale, and multiplex networks*, Science, 328 (2010), pp. 876–878.
- [24] P. MÜLLER, F. QUINTANA, AND G. ROSNER, *A product partition model with regression on covariates*, J. Comput. Graph. Stat., 20 (2011), pp. 260–278.
- [25] M. E. NEWMAN, *Modularity and community structure in networks*, Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A., 103 (2006), pp. 8577–8582.
- [26] M. E. NEWMAN AND M. GIRVAN, *Finding and evaluating community structure in networks*, Phys. Rev. E, 69 (2004), p. 026113.
- [27] K. NOWICKI AND T. A. B. SNIJDERS, *Estimation and prediction for stochastic blockstructures*, J. Am. Stat. Assoc., 96 (2001), pp. 1077–1087.
- [28] S. PAUL AND Y. CHEN, *Consistent community detection in multi-relational data through restricted multi-layer stochastic blockmodel*, Electron. J. Stat., 10 (2016), pp. 3807–3870.
- [29] ———, *Spectral and matrix factorization methods for consistent community detection in multi-layer networks*, Ann. Stat., 48 (2020), pp. 230–250.
- [30] E. REGAZZINI, A. LIJOI, AND I. PRÜNSTER, *Distributional results for means of normalized random measures with independent increments*, Ann. Stat., 31 (2003), pp. 560–585.
- [31] M. N. SCHMIDT AND M. MORUP, *Nonparametric Bayesian modeling of complex networks: an introduction*, IEEE Signal Process. Mag., 30 (2013), pp. 110–128.

- [32] N. STANLEY, S. SHAI, D. TAYLOR, AND P. J. MUCHA, *Clustering network layers with the strata multilayer stochastic block model*, IEEE Trans. Netw. Sci. Eng., 3 (2016), pp. 95–105.
- [33] U. VON LUXBURG, *A tutorial on spectral clustering*, Stat. Comput., 17 (2007), pp. 395–416.
- [34] S. WADE AND Z. GHAHRAMANI, *Bayesian cluster analysis: Point estimation and credible balls*, Bayesian Anal., 13 (2018), pp. 559 – 626.
- [35] J. D. WILSON, J. PALOWITCH, S. BHAMIDI, AND A. B. NOBEL, *Community extraction in multilayer networks with heterogeneous community structure*, J. Mach. Learn. Res., 18 (2017), pp. 5458–5506.
- [36] Y. ZHANG, E. LEVINA, AND J. ZHU, *Community detection in networks with node features*, Electron. J. Stat., 10 (2016), pp. 3153–3178.